

SIMULATION OF A LARGE-SCALE SHAKE TABLE TEST USING PM4SAND PLASTICITY MODEL TO STUDY LIQUEFACTION-INDUCED RESPONSE

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ABSTRACT

Damage dealt with by some recent major earthquakes has raised concerns among the geotechnical engineering community to delve more into the area of soil liquefaction. As part of research funded by Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research (PEER), a large-scale shake table test on a laminar soil box was carried out at the University of California, San Diego, to investigate the effect of liquefaction-induced ground motion on a shallow foundation. In this study, a 2D numerical finite difference simulation of the baseline test was conducted in FLAC using the PM4Sand plasticity model. Some general behavior of sand layers during liquefaction including generation of excess pore water pressure, development of shear and volumetric strain, and their relative contribution to the total settlement were investigated. The model predicted the average final foundation and free-field settlements to be 21.94 cm (measured value 26.05 cm) and 12.36 cm in heave (measured heave value 1.57 cm) respectively. The shear strain appeared to govern the total settlement during seismic excitation compared to volumetric strain, during strong ground motion, while the latter became more apparent after the ground motion had subsided.

Keywords: shake table test, liquefaction, Numerical Analysis, PM4Sand Model, FLAC

INTRODUCTION

Liquefaction-induced settlement during strong ground motion has become one of the most widely studied topics in the field of geotechnical earthquake engineering, especially after the event of 1964 Nigata earthquake. The 1990 Luzon Philippine, 1995 Kobe, 1999 Kocaeli; in recent years the 2010-2011 Canterbury earthquake sequence and 2011 Tohoku earthquake all contain many documented case histories of liquefaction causing devastating damage to structures and foundations (Yoshimi and Tokimatsu 1977; Adachi et al. 1992; Chang 2000; Spence et al. 2003; Yasuda et al. 2012; Cubrinovski 2013). The damage done by these past and recent earthquakes has led researchers to carry out site investigations, and physical and numerical simulations to better understand the contributing mechanism during liquefaction and to seek out viable mitigation measures. Yoshimi and Tokimatsu (1977), based on their scaled 1-g shake table test have developed a relationship between average settlement with liquefiable layer thickness and foundation width. Bray and Dashti (2014) have identified some of the key components of liquefaction-induced ground movement and based on over 1,300 numerical analyses on FLAC 2D it was deduced that most of the deformation during shaking is shear-induced, mostly due to soil-structure interaction (SSI) induced ratcheting and bearing capacity type settlement. In the same study, the volumetric-induced settlement was said to be somewhat significant after the end of strong shaking and largely relates to sedimentation and post-liquefaction reconsolidation (Bray and Dashti 2014). Based on these results, a simplified procedure to calculate liquefaction-induced building settlement was introduced by Bray and Macedo (2017).

Due to the increase in popularity and credibility of computational tools in recent years, numerical simulation has been proven to be a good way to validate physical experiments such as shake table tests and centrifuge tests and to capture field case observations. (e.g., Elgamal et al. 2005; Popescu et al. 2006; Shahir and Pak 2010; Karimi and Dashti 2016a,b). In recent Liquefaction Experiments and Analysis Projects (LEAP), all types of blind predictions (as defined by Lambe 1973) were carried out (Manzari et al. 2018). Using the PM4Sand constitutive soil model, Class A and Class C types of numerical prediction were carried out in FLAC to validate LEAP centrifuge tests (Ziatopoulou 2018).

In this paper, class C1 type numerical prediction of a large-scale shake table test on a shallow foundation in liquefied soil is described. The shake table test was conducted in June 2018 at the large-scale shake table facility at the University of California, San Diego (UCSD) (Jahed Orang et al. 2019, 2021a). The project was funded by the Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center (PEER) with the goals of better understanding the liquefaction mechanism as well as evaluating the effectiveness of countermeasures in mitigating liquefaction-induced settlement. A numerical simulation of a ‘baseline’ test (without any mitigation measures) obtained from fully coupled fluid-mechanical dynamic analysis using the PM4Sand model was conducted. Some basic trends during liquefaction are observed along with experimental results. Similar to the study described in Macedo and Bray (2018), shear and volumetric strain profiles at three different times are observed and it was seen that shear-induced settlement significantly governs total soil deformation during shaking, as was also seen in the study mentioned.

SUMMARY OF LARGE-SCALE SHAKE TABLE TEST

A two-phase experimental study on liquefaction was conducted at UCSD’s Powell Laboratory using a 2.9 m tall soil laminar box, with a 3.9 m length and 1.8 m of width. The elevation view and the plan view of the instrumentation layout and soil models are shown in Fig. 1. In the first phase, the test was conducted without adopting any mitigation measures and is termed a ‘baseline’ test. The second phase involved the use of a group of helical piles as countermeasures, and the result is presented in Jahed Orang et al. (2021b).

The soil model created in the shake table test was deliberately made analogous to the case with shallow liquefiable layers as seen in both Adapazari 1999 Kocaeli earthquake (Bray et al. 2004) and Christchurch 2010-2011 Canterbury Earthquake Sequence (CES) (Cubrinovski 2013) events. The Ottawa F-65 sand was used to build the soil model and the details on soil properties can be found in Bastidas et al. (2017). The input acceleration time history, having a peak ground acceleration of 0.398g corresponding to the Shake 1-1 input motion sequence, is shown in Fig. 2 (Motamed et al. 2020).

The model consists of a dense saturated sand layer at the bottom ($D_r = 87\%$) with a thickness of 1.0 m overlain by a liquefiable loose sand layer ($D_r = 41\%$) of 1.3 m of thickness. A medium-dense ($D_r = 53\%$) sand layer of 0.6 m thickness was placed at the very top as unsaturated surficial crust where a concrete shallow foundation of 1.3 m of width and 0.4 m of embedded depth was placed. As shown in Fig. 1, the contact pressure of the footing was 41.6 kPa which was achieved by placing four columns of steel plates on top of the footing. The density of the concrete in the footing was estimated to be 2616 kg/m³. The laminar soil box consists of 43 steel laminar frames with each having an S3x5.7 steel section. The relative movements of these steel frames allow for a great minimization of boundary effect during shaking.

A full description of the shake table test can be found in Jahed Orang et al. (2019, 2021a). Additional details on the laminar box can be found in Ebeido et al. (2018, 2019a, 2019b).

NUMERICAL MODELING IN FLAC2D

PM4Sand model parameters and soil properties

A fully coupled fluid-mechanical dynamic analysis was performed using the 2D finite-difference program FLAC version 8.0 (Itasca 2016). PM4Sand Version 3.1 constitutive model developed for typical geotechnical earthquake engineering applications was used to simulate Ottawa sand. This is a stress-ratio controlled, critical state compatible bounding surface plasticity model and is known to effectively capture the common trends during liquefaction (Boulanger and Ziotopoulou 2017). In total, PM4Sand (Version 3.1) has 22 input parameters, among which only three are considered primary. They are namely relative density (D_r), Shear modulus coefficient (G_o), and contraction rate parameter (h_{po}) (Boulanger and Ziotopoulou 2017). The shear modulus coefficient relates the elastic shear modulus (G) with atmospheric pressure (P_a) and mean effective confining pressure (σ_m) in the form of the equation,

$$G = G_o P_a \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{P_a} \right)^{0.5}$$

[1]

Fig. 1. Elevation (left) and plan view (right) of instrumentation layout for baseline test from Jahed Orang et al. (2021a) (All units are in mm).

Fig. 2. Input acceleration time history for Shake 1-1 sequence.

The soil properties were obtained following the calibrations done by Bastidas et al. (2017). The parameter G_o is obtained from the derived relationship originally given by Alarcon-Guzman et al. (1989) depending

on the relative density. While calibrating the model parameters, it was seen that changes in the hydraulic conductivity of soil greatly affect the final settlement values, which was also noted by Macedo and Bray (2018). To avoid the occurrence of excessive shear deformation of the elements near the surface to cause the possible termination of the analysis, a very high value of nominal shear resistance was assigned to the top elements in the model near the ground surface.

Building the numerical model

While developing the numerical model, the actual construction sequence of the baseline large-scale shake table test was maintained. The choice of the proper type of interface between soil and foundation was investigated and the *glued* interface was chosen in the final model. The numerical mesh included a total of 589 elements, and the largest element had a size of 0.17m x 0.2m. Static equilibrium was obtained by assigning Mohr-Coulomb constitutive soil models to all the soil layers and right before the application of dynamic loading PM4Sand model was assigned to all the elements, except for the bottom-most elements. The dynamic loading was applied to those elements in the form of shear stress time history, which was converted from the velocity time history (Itasca 2016).

In any numerical model, the selection of accurate boundary conditions is one of the most important factors to obtain a representative output. Although the laminar frames were not directly incorporated into the model, the *attach* command was used to slave the corresponding nodes at the vertical boundaries to simulate the laminar boundary condition. The model base was fixed in both directions during static analysis and quiet boundary condition in the horizontal direction was applied during dynamic analysis. This allows for the proper absorption of the reflected wave in the form of dashpots attached to the base nodes, as proposed by Lysmer and Kuhlemeyer (1969).

A small amount of Rayleigh damping of 0.005 with 5 Hz of central frequency was applied in the model to mitigate numerical noise. The foundation with 0.4 m embedded depth was modeled as an elastic material. Two columns of steel plates were modeled as beam elements, to properly capture the inertial effects and SSI-induced ratcheting (Bray and Dashti 2014) during the simulation. The numerical finite-difference mesh used in the simulation before the application of dynamic load is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1. Numerical model outlying soil models, structural elements, interfaces, and boundary condition at the bottom prior to initiating dynamic loading.

OUTPUTS FROM NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Settlement time history

Similar to the blind prediction competition (Motamed et al. 2020), the settlement time history was recorded in five locations in the 2D model as shown in Fig. 4. LP01/LP02 and LP05/LP06 indicate nodes to capture free-field settlement time history located at 0.75 m from the right and left boundaries respectively. Similarly, nodes SP17, and SP14 record settlement time history at foundation edges 1.3381 m from left and right boundaries respectively, and SP15/SP16 records in the foundation mid-point. The recorded settlement time histories at corresponding nodes from Shake 1-1 sequence as reported in Jahed Orang et al. (2021a) also shown in Fig. 4. Compared to measured data, the FLAC analysis resulted in excessive upward heave in the free-field settlement. The upward heave is the manifestation of the bearing capacity failure of the foundation (Jahed Orang et al. 2021a). A comparable match with the measured data can be seen for the foundation settlement, up to the termination of dynamic loading. The FLAC analysis did not capture the post-liquefaction settlement, which is observed in the Shake 1-1 sequence after the end of shaking. In summary, the model yielded an average foundation settlement of 21.94 cm and an average free-field settlement of 12.36 cm (heave) at $t=25$ sec. The corresponding average measured settlements from the physical test at $t=25$ sec is 26.05 cm and 1.57 cm (heave), respectively. The maximum number of 600 finite-difference elements used in the model due to program restriction and inaccurate representation of laminar boundary conditions are some of the probable reasons behind the predicted excessive upward free-field settlements.

Fig. 2. Free-field (left) and foundation (right) settlement time histories from numerical simulation and measured data.

Generation of excess pore pressure

Excess pore pressure ratio (R_u) generation along with acceleration time histories recorded in the free-field and foundation arrays, in the mid-liquefiable and mid-dense layers, are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. The corresponding R_u time histories from Shake 1-1 loading sequence are also shown (Jahed Orang et al. 2021a). Compared to the measured response, the FLAC analysis appears to have underpredicted and overpredicted the excess pore pressure generation in the mid-liquefiable and mid-dense layers, respectively. In contrast to the actual test, the numerical analysis predicted a steady decrease in R_u values after the end of shaking. As explained in Jahed Orang et al. (2021a), due to high hydraulic transient gradients, both upward and downward flows of pore water were observed, even after the end of shaking. The manifestation of soil ejecta in the unsaturated crust right after the end of shaking also supports the upward flow of pore water from the top of the liquefiable layer (Jahed Orang et al. 2021a). These observations from the physical test explain the persistence of excess pore pressure, even after the end of shaking, which was not captured adequately in the numerical model.

Among all the recorded numerical plots, the excess pore pressure ratio to trigger liquefaction ($R_u = 1.0$) was only seen in the free-field mid-liquefiable layer ($R_u = 1.07$) (Fig. 5). The bottom of the liquefiable layer in free-field also seemed to approach liquefaction ($R_u = 0.98$). The stress bulb resulting from the imposed loading on the foundation by the steel plates eventually led to increased resistance against liquefaction in the corresponding soil region (Macedo and Bray 2018). Seismic excitation during shaking caused the generation of excess pore water pressure i.e. decrease in vertical effective stress. The absence of the stress bulb caused the excess pore-pressure ratios to be higher in the free-field arrays, compared to Foundation arrays.

Fig. 5. Acceleration and excess pore pressure ratio (R_u) time histories in different sensor locations in free-field arrays.

Fig. 6. Acceleration and excess pore pressure ratio (R_u) time histories in different sensor locations in foundation arrays.

Shear and volumetric strain-induced response

As predicted by the numerical model, the shear stress and shear strain time histories in the middle of the dense and liquefiable layers, below the foundation, are shown in Fig. 7, and the stress-strain loops at four different times are also shown. The development of residual shear strain was observed at these two locations, indicating possible accumulation of shear strain at other locations during liquefaction. The area within hysteresis loops became larger as the shaking intensified, a basic trend observed when soil is subjected to dynamic loading.

Fig. 7. Shear stress and strain time histories (upper left) and hysteresis loops (upper right) in the middle of the dense layer; shear stress and strain time histories (lower left) and hysteresis loops (lower right) in the middle of the liquefiable layer, obtained from FLAC analysis.

The shear and volumetric strain developed during liquefaction is investigated in the contour plots related to three different times as shown in Fig. 8. From the study by Macedo and Bray (2018), it has been observed that liquefaction-induced settlement is mainly governed by shear strain controlled mechanism during strong seismic excitation. Similar to that study, the contribution of shear and volumetric strain developed during liquefaction was also investigated here. As the ground motion starts to recede, the contribution of volumetric strain becomes more eminent during the time after strong shaking. Numerical analysis revealed the maximum value of shear strain at the foundation-soil interfaces, and some dilation of medium-dense sand (negative values indicating compression) around the surface and foundation edges (Fig. 8).

The dispersion of shear strain contours is contained above the upper surface of the dense layer, and attained a high value right above the bottom of the liquefiable layer, beneath the foundation. This suggests the potential of greater accumulation of shear strain in the soil if the thickness of the liquefiable layer were higher than 1.3 m, leading to more settlement (Macedo and Bray 2018).

Profiles of shear and volumetric strain at three different times ($t = 5, 11,$ and 25 sec) during shaking, below the mid-foundation are shown in Fig. 9. The comparison shows the relative contribution of shear and volumetric strain in the total settlement. Both the shear and volumetric vertical strain profiles

resemble the triangular shape which can be obtained from adopting the procedure by Schmertmann et al. (1978), suggesting that a triangular-shaped strain profile can be obtained up to 3 m thickness of liquefiable layer; and for higher thickness, the trapezoidal-shaped profile can be observed. As the thickness of the liquefiable layer used in the model was 1.3 m, the numerical result obtained strongly supports the procedure mentioned. All the strains seemed to have reached a maximum value at certain depths and then decreased gradually, especially in the dense layer. The strain profiles show clear dominance of shear strain over the volumetric strain in the liquefiable layer, which diminishes over time as seen from the comparison of the profiles given at $t=11$ sec and $t=25$ sec.

Fig. 8. Trend observed in volumetric and shear strain contour diagrams during shaking: maximum volumetric strain contours at $t = 11$ sec (upper left) and $t = 25$ sec (upper right); maximum shear strain increment contours after initiation of shaking at $t = 11$ sec (lower left) and $t = 25$ sec (lower right).

Fig. 9. Comparison of shear and volumetric strain profiles beneath foundation edge during shaking. The dashed lines mark the boundaries of liquefiable layers.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A fully coupled fluid-mechanical dynamic analysis was carried out with the PM4Sand constitutive model to perform class C1 type prediction of a large-scale shake table experiment. The baseline test was performed in the Powell laboratory of the University of California, San Diego in June 2018, to study the response of soil foundation during liquefaction-induced ground motion. The laminar box used in the test was 1.8 m wide, 3.9 m long, and 2.9 m in height. The middle liquefiable sand layer was 1.3 m thick and had a relative density of 40%. A concrete foundation with a 1.3 m width was embedded into the upper medium dense layer up to 0.4 m depth, and steel plate columns were placed on top of the foundation to create 41.6 kPa contact pressure.

A two-dimensional finite-difference model of the baseline shake table test was created using FLAC 2D to perform simulations. Dynamic loading applied in the numerical model was in accordance with the Shake 1-1 loading sequence from the actual test. Using glued interface yielded better prediction with an average foundation settlement to be 21.94 cm (measured value 26.05 cm) and an average free-field settlement to be 12.36 cm in heave (measured heave value 1.57 cm) at $t = 25$ sec. The excess pore water pressure ratio was predicted higher in free-field array sensor locations compared to the foundation array because of the higher initial effective stress bulb caused by the imposed loading. Compared to the recorded data from the Shake 1-1 sequence, the numerical simulation predicted lower and higher excess pore pressure generation in the mid-liquefiable and mid-dense layers, respectively. In the physical test, a notable high hydraulic transient gradient was observed, leading to the sustained presence of excess pore pressure and the manifestation of soil ejecta after the end of shaking. However, in contrast, the numerical model exhibited a relatively rapid dissipation of excess pore pressure.

The strain history plots indicate the development of residual strain at the end of dynamic loading. Similar to some previous case studies, the settlement is largely governed by the shear strain compared to the volumetric strain during shaking. Some dilation of the medium dense sand layer is seen around the foundation edges and at the surface. The shear strain developed around the foundation-soil interfaces and spread throughout the loose sand layer below the foundation. The final shear strain contour is barely contained by the upper boundary of the dense layer, indicating an increase in the liquefiable layer may have led to an increase in the settlement. The contribution of shear and the volumetric strain was investigated in the form of strain profiles beneath the foundation, and the shear strain seemed to be more significant. The shear strain seemed especially higher within the liquefiable layer, during strong ground motion. As the shaking subsided, the role of volumetric strain in settlement became more apparent.

The discrepancy in observations from the FLAC model and the physical test is likely attributed to three factors: the limited number of finite-difference elements due to program restriction, potentially unrepresentative boundary conditions, and inadequate refinement of model parameters due to time limitation. Nonetheless, the simulation provided valuable insights into the soil-foundation response during liquefaction. Further research should address these limitations to enhance the accuracy and applicability of numerical models, bridging the gap between simulations and physical tests.

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